

MULTISCALE DYNAMICS IN WAFER BONDING: MECHANISMS DRIVING THE BOND FRONT

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Abstract

In direct wafer-to-wafer bonding processes, the bond front is typically observed in a region far from the actual point of gap closure. This far-field region is dominated by a balance of lubrication flow and bending rigidity of the wafer, where the shape of the unbonded region is shown to be of the form $\sim r^{5/3}$. A self-consistent expression for the bond front velocity is derived without relying on any empirical fitting parameters. Numerical estimates are given to delineate the regions where different dissipation mechanisms occur within the expelled gas. Finally, using linear elasticity, the wafer shape deformations due to bonding are linked to the in-plane strains (and hence inherent overlay errors) created by the progressing bond front.

Introduction

Wafer bonding is rich in physics, with the steady-state local adhesion criteria determined at the nanoscale [1], [2] and on global scale by the elastic potential energy of wafers [3]. The *dynamics* of bond front propagation also exhibit rich behaviour: adhesion occurs at nanoscale: namely (a) at the roughness scale of the surfaces for dry bonding, or (b) sub-10 nm gap heights in hydrophilic bonding where hydrogen-bonds form on hydrated bonding surfaces, while the gap being closed itself spans over orders of magnitude (from nm to μm , see Fig 1).

Figure 1 Schematic of the distinct regions along bond front propagation direction. Different physics act on the system at different length scales. Wafer (or gap) shape is denoted by h .

In the presence of all ambient conditions except vacuum, the intervening gas is expelled from the gap due to the advancing bond front. Depending on the gap width, the gas flow is governed by distinct physics: (a) free molecular motion close to the bond front where gap, $h < \lambda$ mean free path and (b) lubrication flow in wider gaps. Similarly, the attractive forces also vary with gap width, ranging from van der Waals, to significantly weaker lubrication pressure. In particular, the wider regions $h \sim O(10s \mu\text{m})$ are exposed to ambient conditions and the attractive pressure sufficient for adhesion only starts to occur for gaps $h \sim O(10s \text{ nm})$.

Results and Discussion

We extend the model of Rieutord et al [4] to show in axisymmetric coordinates that using a balance of lubrication pressure gradients with linear elasticity in the vicinity of the bond front, the unbonded region of the wafer takes a power law shape $\sim A_r r^{5/3}$ [5], where $\sim A_r$ is a

proportionality pre-factor that can be derived in a self-consistent manner theoretically. The bond front velocity U_{lub} is determined in this *far-field region* from an energy balance between the gas flow's viscous dissipation and the work of adhesion [4],[5],[6]. Unlike previously published results, we show that beyond its material parameter dependencies (on Young's modulus E , thickness T , gas viscosity η , mean free path Λ), that meaningful values of the bond front velocity in this far-field regime can only be obtained by limiting the lateral extent over which viscous dissipation is accounted for in the gap, to ultimately derive [5]:

$$U_{lub} = \left(\frac{2187}{70}\right)^{1/4} \frac{\gamma^{5/4}(1-\nu^2)^{1/4}}{(8.91)^{5/4}\eta E^{1/4}t^{3/4}} (\Lambda/2)^{1/2}$$

Using properties of Si(100) 300 mm wafers, symmetrically bonding in standard process conditions, the unbonded gap following the shape $h \sim r^{5/3}$ reaches the lower limit of continuum flow at 68 nm, which lies a distance ~ 0.7 mm from the actual point of gap closure. Similarly, the location corresponding to a gap thickness of 250 nm (which is the resolving limit of infrared, typically used for bond front visualisation) lies ~ 1.5 mm ahead from the bond front. The gas dissipation mechanisms close to the bond front during dynamic propagation of the bond front, and shape of the wafer in this region are unknown. Since the lubrication balance extends over a longer region than the van der Waal's adhesion region and constitutes the rate-limiting step for the bond front's velocity, an assumption may be made that the substrate shape $h \sim A_r r^{5/3}$ [4],[5] may extend down to the smaller length scales close to the bond front.

Given the wafer thickness of 775um is small compared to the distance over which bond wave travels, linear elasticity can be used and shear strains in the material can be neglected to write the strain field as $\epsilon \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dh}{dr}\right)^2$. For the bond front located at position r_b , the strain due to bond front progression in the unbonded region is $\epsilon \approx \frac{25 A_r}{72} (r - r_b)^{4/3}$. As the bond front reaches the edge of the wafer, the region available over which viscous dissipation occurs shrinks, leading to an increase in the bond front velocity. As adhesion forces become dominant, the wafer shape is not balanced by lubrication pressure alone, and bending strains must be included along with the geometric strain written above. These higher strains can also be observed with a patterned wafer geometry (PWG) metrology tool in regions on the bonded wafer where the bond front is interrupted (for example due to vacuum-clamping wafer(s)' edges). The higher strains along the edges can explain why higher runout components of wafer-to-wafer bonder overlays are typically observed in the edge region.

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